

University of Venda

Unstructured data collection tool

HIV-Positive mothers (Pregnant or breastfeeding, non-adherent to ART)

The interview guide is designed to gather in-depth insights into the complexities of maternal ART adherence and its impact on mother-to-child transmission of HIV. The guide consists of two sections, with demographics as the first section, followed by section two, consisting of central questions aimed at understanding the personal experiences, barriers, support systems, and suggestions for improving ART adherence and reducing MTCT. It is intended for use with individuals living with HIV during pregnancy or breastfeeding.

Section A: Demographic information

Age:

Marital status:

Number of children:

Age of youngest child / Gestational age if pregnant:

Highest level of education:

ART initiation date:

Current ART adherence status (last time medication was taken):

Place of residence (urban/rural):

Section B: Central interview question

May you kindly share with me your experiences of living with HIV and taking ART as a mother?